

Chronic Idiopathic Constipation: Etiology and Recovery

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 📅 March 26, 2025

Published: 📅 April 04, 2025

Citation: Xinghong Yang. Chronic Idiopathic Constipation: Etiology and Recovery. Biomed J Sci & Tech Res 61(2)-2025. BJSTR. MS.ID.009571.

ABSTRACT

Chronic idiopathic constipation (CIC) is a common yet poorly understood gastrointestinal disorder with limited effective treatments. Modern medicine attributes CIC to impaired intestinal motility, gut-brain axis dysfunction, and microbial imbalances, but these explanations fail to account for cases where conventional therapies prove ineffective. From a Dharma perspective, CIC arises from karmic obstacles, with spiritual interference playing a significant role in its manifestation. This study explores the karmic nature of CIC and presents cases in which Buddhist practices—such as making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and performing life liberation—have led to complete recovery. The findings highlight the limitations of a purely materialistic medical approach and suggest that integrating Dharma practices may offer a path to true healing. Based on these insights, we propose redefining the term “idiopathic” in “chronic idiopathic constipation” to reflect its origins in “karma (业障) and spirits (灵性),” rather than adhering to the Cambridge Dictionary definition, which states that “an idiopathic disease or medical condition has no known cause.” Accordingly, “chronic idiopathic constipation” should be re-named “chronic karmic constipation” or “chronic spiritual constipation.”

Keywords: Chronic Idiopathic Constipation; Karma; Spirits; Healing; Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door

Introduction

Chronic idiopathic constipation (CIC) is a prevalent functional gastrointestinal disorder characterized by persistent difficulties in defecation, reduced bowel movement frequency, and a sensation of incomplete evacuation [1]. It significantly impacts quality of life, places a burden on healthcare systems, and contributes to substantial economic costs. Affecting approximately 10–17% of the global population, CIC is more common among females and the elderly and can lead to debilitating symptoms [2].

Current treatment options for CIC remain limited in balancing efficacy and safety [1]. Available therapies include medications [3], non-pharmacologic auxiliary treatments [4], probiotics [5], vibrating capsules [6], surgery [7], and others. Despite advancements in pharmaceutical research, the medical management of CIC remains suboptimal [8]. Auxiliary therapies can serve as effective complementary treatments but must be used alongside standard medical care [4].

When a disease proves difficult to treat through conventional medicine, it is often rooted in karmic obstacles or spiritual causes. Seeking help through Dharma may offer a more effective path to heal-

ing [9]. For instance, patient Z21’s father with Alzheimer’s disease, who had been constipated for eight days, spontaneously had a bowel movement on the second day of playing the *Great Compassion Mantra* chanted by a hundred voices at home [10].

This study aims to further investigate the potential karmic nature of CIC and explore whether Buddhist practices of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door can serve as an effective treatment or even lead to a complete cure.

For those who have never encountered Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door and may not be familiar with some terms and concepts in the text, please refer to the previous publications for general insights [9,11].

Etiology

In the scientific community, CIC, also known as functional constipation, has no identifiable organic cause [12]. According to the Rome IV criteria, functional gastrointestinal and bowel disorders result from inappropriate gut-brain interactions. Their pathophysiology is complex and poorly understood [13]. The precise pathogenesis of CIC remains unclear, with core mechanisms including impaired intestinal

motility, abnormal signaling within the enteric nervous system, and an imbalance in gut microbiota [14]. Notably, the term “idiopathic” is defined by the Cambridge Dictionary as referring to “an idiopathic disease or medical condition has no known cause.”

When the cause of a disease cannot be identified by doctors, it is often rooted in karma with manifestations of spiritual interference [9]. To effectively address karmic and spiritual diseases, one should seek guidance through Dharma practices. Below are 2 Dharma question and answer (Q&A) dialogues in which Dharma Master Jun Hong Lu teaches how to treat CIC effectively.

Q&A 1. How to Recite Buddhist Scriptures for CIC [15]?

Caller

Hello, Master! A fellow practitioner suffers from severe constipation with heavy bleeding. Despite consulting both Western and Chinese medicine, no treatment has been effective. Others are surprised that someone so young has such severe constipation. What Buddhist scriptures should he recite?

Master

This is a karmic illness affecting blood circulation. If he has already been reciting scriptures for a while without improvement, he may need surgery. His daily recitation should include:

- 1) 49 times the *Great Compassion Mantra*;
- 2) 21 times the *Heart Sutra*;
- 3) 3 times the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*;
- 4) Release 200 fish within 1-1.5 months.

He should also make a vow never to eat live sea animals again.

Start with a batch of 21 Little Houses first. If the condition improves and the bleeding stops within a month, it indicates that the scripture recitation is effective. As with other cases, he must dedicate time to reciting scriptures and performing life liberation to see results.

Caller

Within 1-1.5 months?

Master

If there is no improvement, surgery may be necessary, which suggests deep-rooted karmic obstacles.

Q&A 2. What Causes Years of CIC [16]?

Caller

Hello, Master! I am from Shenzhen, China. I got through on the phone in September. Please check for a woman born in 1979, Year of the Sheep, who has suffered from CIC for many years.

Master

Her intestines are blocked—it’s full of fish spirits inside!

Caller

Yes, she loves eating fish.

Master

She even prefers freshly killed ones!

Caller

That’s right...

Master

I see only fish heads, no tails. This is severely shortening her lifespan.

Caller

Does she need to recite Little Houses?

Master

No, calculate the total number of fish she has eaten and multiply by three—that is the number of times she should recite the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*. Recite diligently.

From Master Lu’s answers, we learn that CIC may stem from karma or spiritual factors. Karmic and spiritual issues should be addressed through Dharma practices.

Recovery

Regarding recovery from CIC, Master Lu provided guidance through dialogues with His disciples. Below are three conversations in which Master Lu explained how to address CIC.

Q&A 3. How to Address CIC from Long-Term Meat Consumption [17]?

Caller

Hello, Master! Some people have been eating meat for many years, and now they are experiencing chronic constipation. What should they do?

Master

Their intestines are already damaged. Those who consume meat for decades will inevitably suffer from intestinal decay in old age. What does constipation indicate? Think about it—meat, whether dead or alive, can fuse together. In surgery, they used to use catgut sutures, which naturally integrate with the body without removal. Likewise, when you consume dead meat, it accumulates in your intestines. When constipation occurs, the dead meat clogs the intestines, decays, and rots, affecting the living tissue. Over time, this decay can lead to colon cancer.

Caller

If someone has switched to a vegetarian diet, practices Buddhism, and recites Buddhist scriptures, what else can they do?

Master

If the condition is severe, surgery may be necessary.

Caller

What if it is not severe?

Master

If it is not severe, they should diligently follow a vegetarian diet and rely on Guan Yin Bodhisattva's blessings. In the past, Bodhisattvas frequently appeared in people's dreams because people were purer. Some would dream of a divine hand pressing on the afflicted area, and upon waking, they were healed. However, whether one receives such blessings depends on their past merits and the strength of their vows.

Caller: Even seeing a gentleman in a black suit would be great (The caller indicates Master Lu)!

Master

Haha, yes, that one is quite active and often on the move.

Caller

What traditional Chinese medicine is good for constipation?

Master

It is best to take digestive aids, such as Xiang Sha or spleen-strengthening medicines like Jian Pi Wan.

Caller

Thank you, Master!

Q&A 4. How to Recite Scriptures for a Child Born with CIC [18]?**Caller**

Hello, Master! A child has suffered from severe constipation since birth. What scriptures should be recited?

Master

For stubborn constipation, recite more of the *Heart Sutra*, the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, and Little Houses.

Caller

What about the *Great Compassion Mantra*?

Master

Recite 7 times the *Great Compassion Mantra*, 21 times the *Heart Sutra*, and offer more Little Houses, 17 Little Houses for the first batch.

Caller

How many times for the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* daily?

Master

Two times is sufficient.

Caller

The child is three years old and still wets the bed at night.

Master

That is fine—it will soon improve. Once you continue reciting these scriptures, the condition will resolve. Also, release 150 fish for the child.

Caller

Thank you, Master!

Q&A 5. How to Relieve CIC in the Elderly [19]?**Caller**

Elderly individuals in their 70s or 80s often experience dry stools and constipation. Besides eating bananas and honey, what scriptures should they recite?

Master

They should recite the *Xiao Zai Ji Xiang Shen Zhou* and the *Heart Sutra*. Also, their diet should be low in fat. Constipation is linked to blood circulation issues, so they should drink more water to prevent blood viscosity, which contributes to constipation.

Caller

I see.

Results**Case 1. Overcoming CIC Through the Three Golden Buddhist Practices**

I am a hospital nurse. My job is often demanding and hectic. Due to my irregular work schedule and the inability to use the restroom on time, I gradually developed constipation in the early 2000s. This condition troubled me for many years, at its worst, I could only have a bowel movement once in twelve days.

Back then, I had not yet encountered Buddhism or begun spiritual cultivation, so I did not understand that illnesses could be categorized as physical and spiritual ailments. I only treated it as a physical disease. As a medical professional, I sought help from renowned doctors and consulted all the professors in my hospital. I tried countless medications and folk remedies, but nothing worked. Even enemas had no effect. No matter what method I tried, nothing could relieve my suffering.

The most severe episode lasted over ten days without a bowel movement, causing toxin accumulation in my body and a series of discomforts. My complexion turned dull and gray, my eyes looked lifeless, and I suffered from significant hair loss. My sweat glands had shut down completely—I could not sweat at all. Whether playing basketball or engaging in other physical activities, while others sweated profusely, I remained completely dry. It was a terrible experience. Whenever someone recommended a remedy for constipation, I would immediately try it.

However, none of them worked. Despite having access to the best medical resources and trying various treatments, I found no relief, which left me in great distress.

Guan Yin Bodhisattva is compassionate and responsive to the suffering of sentient beings. By chance, a colleague at our hospital told me, “Teacher Z, life liberation is very beneficial.” She only practiced life liberation without reciting Buddhist scriptures, and I joined them in liberating animals. During the process, I met Buddhist practitioners from a Dharma door who advised me to recite Buddhist scriptures and explained the concept of karma elimination. At the time, I did not understand much, but I followed their advice with sincerity. Thus, I practiced that Dharma door for two years and gained some Buddhist knowledge, but my constipation showed no significant improvement.

Later, I came across Master Lu’s teaching in *Buddhism in Plain Terms* (Volume 1, Chapter 9), which stated: “Some Dharma doors may not be suitable for you. Dharma and Dharma doors have a time frame and change with the times. In the past, Buddhism encouraged renunciation and monastic life, but now it emphasizes lay practice—cultivating oneself while living in the world. Therefore, Dharma doors also evolve accordingly.”

In 2017, I practiced life liberation occasionally, but it was not until 2019 that I truly embarked on the path of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

From 2017 onward, I continued with life liberation. I finally encountered the great benefactors in my life in 2019—fellow Buddhist practitioners of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door! These practitioners were incredibly kind and enthusiastic, teaching me that Buddhist practice requires one to recite Buddhist scriptures, accumulate merits and virtues, and repent for past mistakes. They sent me Buddhist scriptures and Dharma Gems, but no one followed up or guided me, so I did not fully understand them.

Consequently, these Dharma Gems remained unused for six months while I continued practicing my previous Dharma door. Looking back, I realize that my affinity was not yet mature, leading me to a detour in my spiritual journey. Truly, “a good Dharma master is hard to find, and the right Dharma door is difficult to encounter.”

In 2019, a colleague who practiced Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door suggested, “Teacher Z, you should try this Dharma door. It is incredi-

bly effective and can help solve many real-life problems.” I asked her how to begin, and she instructed me to start by reciting daily Buddhist scriptures and then progress to reciting Little Houses, which help transcend spirits and eliminate karmic obstacles.

Following her guidance, I began daily recitations and, after becoming familiar with them, started reciting Little Houses. Previously, I had been fond of eating meat. After hearing Master Lu’s teachings about the benefits of vegetarianism in enhancing the effects of scripture recitation, I made a vow to adopt a vegetarian diet and continue practicing life liberation. Master Lu often emphasized that excessive meat consumption could lead to constipation and even cancer.

Sadly, I had not encountered Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door or Master Lu earlier; otherwise, I would have understood these truths sooner.

As I deepened my practice, I sought guidance from fellow practitioners whenever I had doubts. I once had recurring dreams of many children, and fellow practitioners reminded me to recite Little Houses to help my aborted children ascend. After burning several hundred Little Houses for them, I dreamt of a beautifully dressed child visiting me, followed by another dream of two children bathing. Based on Master Lu’s Q&A teachings, I understood that these children had received the Little Houses and were in a better state.

Before practicing Buddhism, my dreams were often nightmares—I dreamt of snakes coiling around me, being chased, and experiencing spirit oppression (sleep paralysis) [20]. When I first started practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, I had a terrifying dream where someone was hunting me down, imprisoning me, and preparing to execute me. Master Lu explained that dreaming of snakes signifies troubles, and being chased indicates karmic creditors seeking repayment.

After sharing this dream with my Buddhist colleague, she advised me to urgently recite Little Houses to help ascend these spirits. Apart from reciting Little Houses for my aborted children, I also recited many for my own karmic creditors. Whenever I dreamt of a deceased person, I would burn 21 Little Houses for them. Whenever I had a negative dream, I would promptly offer Little Houses and pray to Guan Yin Bodhisattva for good health and peace. Over time, these terrifying nightmares gradually disappeared, my dreams became more auspicious, and my constipation significantly improved.

Over the years, I deeply repented for my past abortions, continuously reciting the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* and offering Little Houses for my unborn children and karmic creditors. Alongside my commitment to vegetarianism and life liberation, I accumulated merits and virtues, and my chronic constipation unknowingly disappeared! I was overjoyed because this condition had tormented me for over a decade, and no medical treatment had helped.

Through the Three Golden Buddhist Practices taught by Master Lu—making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and performing life

liberation—I completely cured my CIC! I am incredibly grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva, my revered Master Lu, and my fellow practitioners, whose selfless care and support touched me deeply.

Now, four years into retirement and seven years into Buddhist practice, I have never stopped reciting Little Houses. I now incorporate Master Lu's Five Golden Buddhist Practices into my spiritual cultivation. My vow is to practice life liberation and vegetarianism for life, become one of the Guan Yin Bodhisattva's thousand hands and eyes, help destined sentient beings worldwide, repent for my karmic obstacles, study *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, and integrate Buddhism into daily life—never quitting from the path! I sincerely hope my experience will inspire more people to embrace Buddhism, take up Buddhist scripture recitation, and attain good health and a life free from suffering!

Shared by: X100

Case 2. Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door Cured My Daughter's CIC

My daughter had suffered from constipation since she was about one year old. We tried various treatments, but none were particularly effective. Initially, I thought constipation was a common issue among young children, so I did not pay much attention to it.

However, starting in May 2013, her condition worsened. At first, she would have a bowel movement every 2-3 days, but later, it became once every 4-5 days. She experienced severe pain during bowel movements, often accompanied by bleeding. The suffering from constipation made her resist defecation entirely, turning every attempt into a battle that left both my husband and me utterly exhausted. We were deeply concerned about her health.

With the guidance and support of fellow Buddhist practitioners, I began adding 21 recitations of the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* and 21 recitations of the *Heart Sutra* to my daughter's daily recitation. Additionally, I made a vow to recite Little Houses for her, completing them in batches of 21. The Little Houses proved to be incredibly effective—each time I completed and burned a batch of 21, her constipation improved a bit. By April or May 2014, she suddenly started going to the bathroom on her own, sometimes even twice a day, and her CIC was completely cured! She became healthier and happier.

During the year of reciting Buddhist scriptures to help my daughter, there were times when her condition relapsed, and I lost confidence. I felt discouraged, believing that her karmic obstacles were too heavy and that reciting scriptures might not have an immediate effect. However, each time, I found renewed faith through Guan Yin Bodhisattva's blessings, the encouragement of fellow practitioners, and the positive energy I gained from *Buddhism in Plain Terms*. These gave me the strength to persist in reciting scriptures and offering Little Houses for her karmic creditors.

Indeed, as the saying goes, "With dedication, even an iron rod can

be ground into a needle!" The effort brings rewards. Through this personal experience, I want to encourage all fellow Buddhist practitioners to stay steadfast in their faith and persist in reciting scriptures, making vows, and performing life liberation. If you encounter obstacles, sincerely seek Guan Yin Bodhisattva's blessings, communicate with fellow practitioners, read *Buddhism in Plain Terms* more often, and listen to Master Lu's Dharma talks more frequently—you will surely receive Guan Yin Bodhisattva's compassionate blessings and protection!

Dharma practitioner: Q101

Case 3. Buddhism Allowed Me to Discard the Crutch I Had Relied on for 25 Years; My Heart Disease, CIC, Insomnia, and Hypertension Healed Without Medication

Before I encountered Buddhism, I was plagued by various illnesses. Since suffering a stroke in 2000, I have been left with lasting impairments in my right hand and foot, relying on a crutch to walk. Additionally, I had been battling heart disease for 25 years, along with CIC, insomnia, and hypertension. These ailments made me feel extremely inferior and irritable, leaving me with a perpetually sorrowful expression. My life had no quality, and I was in constant suffering. However, the great compassion of the Bodhisattva led me to Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, which completely changed my life!

I am deeply grateful to the fellow Buddhist practitioner who introduced me to Buddhism. She told me that through practicing Buddhism and reciting Buddhist scriptures, my health could be restored. At first, I was skeptical. On November 2, 2023, I received Dharma Gems and brought them home, marking the beginning of my Buddhist practice. I started reciting scriptures and chanting the holy name of Guan Yin Bodhisattva.

One day, I read a fellow practitioner's sharing, whose condition was similar to mine. Through Buddhist practice, she recovered, which greatly inspired me. I added her as a friend and asked her how she achieved it. She told me, "By applying the Five Golden Buddhist Practices—making vows, reciting scriptures, performing life liberation, reading *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, and practicing deep repentance—you can also recover! As long as you have faith, make vows, and take action, the Bodhisattva will bless you!" She even sent me Dharma books and Dharma Gems for free and taught me how to use the Five Golden Buddhist Practices to eliminate karma and repay karmic debts. She encouraged me to practice diligently, assuring me that Guan Yin Bodhisattva always responds to prayers.

I studied and recited them with dedication. Although the *Great Compassion Mantra* was challenging to learn at first, I persevered and eventually mastered it. I never missed an opportunity to recite it, even during my morning walks. I constantly chanted the holy name of Guan Yin Bodhisattva, read *Buddhism in Plain Terms* daily, and frequently performed life liberation. Applying the Five Golden Buddhist Practices, I sincerely prayed to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to save me.

At first, burning Little Houses was difficult because my right hand was impaired from the stroke. I had to use my left hand to hold the lighter, but my right hand couldn't grasp the tweezers. My husband had to assist me. The great compassion of Guan Yin Bodhisattva shone upon me. One night, She appeared in my dream and instructed me to use my legs to hold the tweezers. When I woke up, I immediately understood and followed Her guidance, successfully burning Little Houses one by one.

I am immensely grateful for the Bodhisattva's divine guidance! The power of Buddhist scriptures is truly incredible—Dharma can transform everything, and the Buddhas and Bodhisattvas are the supreme healers! Even my long-standing hypertension improved, and I no longer needed medication to control it. My blood pressure returned to normal! I was overjoyed—Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is truly miraculous! This further strengthened my confidence in Buddhist practice.

After Three Months of Practicing Buddhism, I Discarded the Crutch I Had Relied on for 25 Years

Due to the karmic consequences of my past and present lives, I unfortunately suffered a stroke at the age of 35, which left me disabled in my right hand and foot. I was always afraid of falling while walking, so I had to rely on a crutch, which accompanied me for 25 years.

One day, three months into my Buddhist practice, I dreamt of Guan Yin Bodhisattva, who told me to put down my crutch. I hesitated and said, "I am afraid—what if I fall?" Guan Yin Bodhisattva gently reassured me, "You don't need to be afraid, I am here with you." When I woke up, I was filled with Dharma joy. I truly put down the crutch!

Previously, I would get exhausted and breathless after walking just a short distance and would have to rest frequently. Now, I can walk just like a normal person and even walk for an hour every day! My gratitude to Guan Yin Bodhisattva for Her compassionate blessings is beyond words!

My Severe Constipation of Over Twenty Years Was Cured

I suffered from severe CIC. I couldn't relieve myself at all, and every bowel movement left me in tears from pain! Initially, I relied on laxatives, but when they stopped working, I had to resort to enemas. My husband had to assist me with this agonizing process every time. It was unbearable!

At the time, I thought to myself that I would be willing to pay 10,000 CNY (~\$1,380) if it meant I could relieve myself normally just once.

After starting my Buddhist practice, I prayed daily to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to help me overcome constipation. Guan Yin Bodhisattva is truly compassionate: a child calls upon their mother, and the mother always hears. Not long after, my CIC disappeared, and I have been

able to relieve myself smoothly once every day. I am deeply grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva!

My Heart Disease of Over 20 Years Healed Without Medication

A year after my stroke, I underwent major heart surgery to replace two heart valves. I was hospitalized for six months. Due to the stroke, the surgery did not go as well as expected, and the doctor warned that I would need another operation in a few years.

For years, I suffered from poor heart health—chest tightness, palpitations, shortness of breath, and severe atrial fibrillation. Walking even a short distance required me to sit down and catch my breath.

However, after less than a year of Buddhist practice, all these symptoms disappeared! My heart disease was essentially cured! The boundless power of Dharma is beyond imagination!

My Insomnia of Over 20 Years Disappeared

In less than a year of practicing Buddhism, my body underwent incredible transformations! Previously, I suffered from unbearable chronic insomnia and had to take two sleeping pills every night to fall asleep. However, after diligently burning Little Houses for my karmic creditors, my insomnia disappeared. I can now sleep soundly through the night without any medication!

Before falling ill, I weighed 136 pounds, but the suffering of my illnesses reduced me to a frail 105 pounds. I was so emaciated that I felt extremely self-conscious and avoided social interactions. Friends and acquaintances would comment on how thin I had become. Now, with the blessings of the Bodhisattva, my many illnesses have healed, my weight has returned to 119 pounds, and I am healthy and happy. The smile that had long disappeared from my face has returned. I now actively greet people when I see them, and they are astonished: "You are not using a crutch anymore?"

My complexion has improved, and I no longer look sickly. I feel full of vitality, exercise daily, and can walk for an hour without fatigue. I am filled with Dharma joy every day! Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is truly extraordinary, miraculous, and absolutely genuine. Those who practice it will reap its benefits!

Fellow Practitioner: J102

Case 4. Reciting Buddhist Scriptures Cured My Years-Long CIC

After graduating from university, I suddenly developed CIC. This issue troubled me for nearly ten years.

During this period, I sought treatment from traditional Chinese medicine practitioners and took herbal medicine, but it did not cure me. The longest time I took herbal medicine was in 2021 when I drank it for a full three months. However, my symptoms fluctuated, and in the end, just the sight of the medicine could make me feel nauseous and unable to continue.

On the 19th day of the ninth lunar month in 2023, I encountered Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door and began reciting the *Great Compassion Mantra*. After a few days, my constipation significantly improved. However, one day, the symptoms reappeared.

My family has practiced Buddhism and maintained a vegetarian diet for generations. I was born into a vegetarian family and have never eaten meat. So, I sought guidance from the Buddhist practitioner who introduced me to the practice. The practitioner asked me, "Have you ever killed flies or mosquitoes?" I replied, "Quite a lot. I studied at a university in the south of China, where mosquitoes were abundant, and they always seemed to target me."

She then advised me to recite the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*. Initially, I recited it 21 times daily. After a week, my bowel movements became normal. Later, I increased to 49 recitations per day and have continued ever since.

By the time of this sharing, I had been reciting the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* for more than two months. My constipation only briefly relapsed before the Spring Festival, but after the festival, I have had no concerns about bowel movements. The power of Buddhist scriptures is truly incredible.

The power of Dharma is boundless. Those who believe will be liberated. I hope more destined sentient beings will have faith in Buddhism, recite scriptures, receive blessings, and be freed from suffering!

Fellow practitioner: B103

Case 5. Decades of CIC and Bloating Healed Naturally Through Practicing Buddhism, Adopting a Vegetarian Diet, and Reciting Buddhist Scriptures!

For as long as I can remember, I never had regular bowel movements. When I was in middle school and lived on campus, I rarely used the restroom at school and would usually only relieve myself once a week when I returned home. At the time, I didn't think it was abnormal.

However, over the years, my digestion worsened, and my abdomen became increasingly bloated. By my 30s, the condition had deteriorated to the point where I would go ten days, half a month, or even longer without a bowel movement. My stomach was unbearably bloated, and after every meal, I couldn't sit comfortably because my digestion was sluggish, causing my abdomen to feel tight and distended. I often could only eat half a small bowl per meal, yet I wouldn't feel hungry. I frequently burped but never passed gas. Living like this was unbearable.

I sought both Western and Chinese medical treatments, but none provided relief. It wasn't until I was 38 years old that I encountered Buddhism and realized that my condition was a result of karmic illness. Due to my ignorance in the past, I had killed and consumed

many living beings, including fish, shrimp, chicken, and ducks. I came to understand that hospitals could not cure such conditions. If left unchecked, my situation would only worsen in a vicious cycle. The only way to eliminate karmic debts was through making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and performing life liberation.

I made a few vows to Guan Yin Bodhisattva:

- 1) Be a vegetarian for life;
- 2) Release a specific number of fish;
- 3) Recite a specific number of Little Houses to repay my karmic debts;
- 4) Sincerely repent for the transgressions I had committed due to my ignorance.

Every day, I diligently recited Buddhist scriptures, repented my past wrong deeds, recited Little Houses, and performed life liberation. Additionally, I supported fellow Buddhist practitioners by gifting Buddhist chanting machines, attending Master Lu's Dharma conferences, and helping others connect with Buddhism.

At some point, I unconsciously noticed that my CIC had significantly improved, and eventually, it was completely healed! Now, I have normal daily bowel movements, no more bloating, and I can eat and drink with ease. The unbearable tightness in my abdomen is gone, and my digestive system functions smoothly.

Before becoming a vegetarian, I used to feel sleepy after meals. However, after adopting a vegetarian diet over the past few years, my body has become much lighter, my digestion has no burden, and I no longer feel drowsy after eating. Once you get used to vegetarianism, it feels completely natural, and you begin to appreciate the pure and authentic flavors of plant-based foods. In contrast, meat smells foul, carrying an animal odor that is repulsive!

When we hear the agonizing screams of animals being slaughtered, can we still bear to eat their flesh? Animals, just like humans, are sentient beings with consciousness and emotions—they simply cannot speak. By consuming their flesh, you provoke their spirits, and they will seek retribution! Please do not let ignorance bring endless suffering upon ourselves. For the sake of our own health and that of our family, please choose vegetarianism!

Due to our ignorance, we accumulate countless karmic debts, such as killing, eating live creatures, abortion, verbal abuse, greed, jealousy, hatred, theft, sexual misconduct, etc. These actions lead to illness, career setbacks, relationship conflicts, disobedient children, and many other sufferings. Without learning Buddhism, one would never know the root causes of their pain and misfortunes, bringing endless suffering to themselves and their families!

Fortunately, Buddhism reveals the truth to us, teaching us how to eliminate suffering, restore health, achieve family harmony, and attain success.

Life in this world is filled with worries and suffering, but Buddhism can help us overcome all kinds of challenges and attain true happiness. All sentient beings possess Buddha nature—the earlier we embrace Buddhism, the sooner we will benefit. Practicing Buddhism costs nothing, yet it can solve your fundamental problems.

Please open a Buddhist scripture book. Changing our destiny is just a single thought away!

Fellow practitioner: L104

Case 6. The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door Is Genuine and Effective—The Miraculous Recovery of My CIC

In April 2018, a fellow practitioner called me and said, “Auntie, practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door and reciting Little Houses is incredibly effective.” At that time, since my affinity with Buddha had not yet matured, I didn’t take it seriously and didn’t give it much thought.

On the fifth day of the ninth lunar month in 2018, which was a Sunday, I was sitting downstairs at my home, reading a book of four-character idioms that teach people to be compassionate. I read for about an hour. Suddenly, I recalled what the fellow practitioner had told me over the phone about the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. So, I called her. Since she was at work, I decided to visit her workplace. There, she explained the extraordinary benefits of this Dharma practice.

I knew that she had been in poor health, but after diligently practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, her condition had significantly improved. After learning about the remarkable benefits of this Dharma Door, I went to her home that very night to invite Buddhist scriptures and Dharma Gems. I invited them all back home and immediately began learning to recite the *Great Compassion Mantra*, the *Heart Sutra*, other daily recitations, and the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*. I practiced diligently for three days.

Since I didn’t have a Buddhist altar at home, I could only offer incense in my heart to the Bodhisattva. I made a few vows to Guan Yin Bodhisattva:

- 1) Become a lifelong vegetarian;
- 2) Recite Buddhist scriptures;
- 3) Perform daily recitations.

Additionally, I released captive animals every day for Master Lu, myself, and my children, regardless of the weather.

During the first three days of my daily recitation, whenever I recited the *Great Compassion Mantra*, my stomach would rumble like a moving train. At that time, I didn’t understand that it was my intestines becoming active again. After completing my recitations, I had the urge to go to the bathroom. Soon after, my CIC, which had plagued me for many years, completely disappeared. I realized how miracu-

lous and effective the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door truly is! I am deeply grateful to Namo Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva for bringing this extraordinary and efficacious Dharma Door to us suffering beings!

When I first started reciting scriptures, I kept wondering whether the Bodhisattva was blessing me. One night, in my sleep, I heard a voice saying, “You ask every day whether Guan Yin Bodhisattva is blessing you, but in reality, the Bodhisattva is always watching over and protecting you.” Upon waking, I felt so ashamed of my ignorance. Without the compassionate salvation of Guan Yin Bodhisattva, I might not even be alive today.

After practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, my various ailments gradually healed. Previously, I had a ligament injury and joint problems in my hand, making it impossible to bend my fingers when extended. I couldn’t even lift objects at work, and this condition had persisted for about twenty years. Although I never specifically prayed to the Bodhisattva for this issue, through my consistent vows, scripture recitation, and life liberation, Guan Yin Bodhisattva compassionately healed my hand.

The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is truly a miraculous practice that relieves the suffering of sentient beings! The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is real and effective! We must diligently follow Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Lu in our spiritual cultivation to be liberated from suffering and attain happiness!

Dharma Practitioner: D105

Case 7. The End of an Unspoken Struggle—The Miraculous Three Golden Buddhist Practices Helped Me Overcome 20 Years of CIC

I first encountered the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door at the end of 2013. A former classmate gifted me one of Master Lu’s books, and I was deeply fascinated by the miraculous accuracy of His Totem readings and the life-changing experiences shared by fellow practitioners after practicing Buddhism and reciting scriptures. This marked the beginning of my unbreakable bond with the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

Since I started practicing, my life has been filled with Dharma joy every day! Both my health and life have undergone incredible transformations. Take my 20-plus years of CIC as an example. I had suffered from it since high school. For over two decades, I endured the frustration of going three to five days without any bowel movements. I often had to rely on laxatives, suppositories, or detox enzymes to force relief. I had tried countless medications and dietary adjustments, but nothing worked. The suffering was beyond what most people could imagine.

After practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door and applying Master Lu’s Three Golden Buddhist Practices—making vows, reciting

scriptures, and performing life liberation—I persisted for a period of time, and then a miracle happened! My condition gradually improved, and now my CIC is completely gone.

I am deeply grateful to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva for Her compassionate salvation! I also sincerely thank Master Lu for His Dharma teachings, which have helped me resolve such a major issue in my life.

At the same time, I want to encourage new practitioners who may still be hesitant—Guan Yin Bodhisattva truly exists, and the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is real and effective. With great compassion, Guan Yin Bodhisattva responds to all sincere prayers. The Three Golden Buddhist Practices can resolve any difficulties in life.

Shared by: L106

Discussion

Humans, as living beings, consume food, which is then digested, and waste must be excreted. Difficulty in urination can lead to illness [21], and the same applies to difficulty in defecation.

No one wants to experience CIC, as it is a highly distressing condition for those affected. To alleviate patients' suffering, scientists have been working tirelessly to address this issue. Despite various hypotheses and numerous treatment developments, CIC remains prevalent, and existing therapies are not always effective or ideal. This situation suggests that science has yet to fully grasp the root causes of CIC, let alone discover a definitive solution.

If astronomers only observe the sky during the day and never at night, they would have a severely limited understanding of the universe. Their textbooks would only describe the Sun and Earth, completely ignoring the Moon and the countless stars.

Similarly, if medical scientists study illnesses solely from a materialistic perspective, they are like astronomers who observe only the daytime sky, overlooking a crucial aspect of health. They may fail to recognize the influence of unseen spirits on a patient's well-being. However, many illnesses have spiritual origins, and spirits, like the millions of stars that emerge only in the night sky, remain invisible to the ordinary human eye.

Dharma encompasses both the materialistic and spiritual perspectives of the universe, much like an astronomer who studies the sky both during the day and at night.

From a materialistic perspective, Dharma teaches sentient beings to let go. We enter this world with nothing and will leave with nothing. The only things we truly carry with us are merits and virtues, and karma [9]. Letting go of excessive attachment to the material world fosters mental well-being, which in turn influences physical health, ultimately leading to overall harmony of mind and body. This aligns with scientific findings that physical and mental health are mutually influential [22].

From a spiritual perspective, Dharma acknowledges that human existence does not simply cease with death. While the physical body decays, the soul continues to exist and transitions into a spiritual realm, making the destination of this journey profoundly significant. Science has yet to fully embrace this spiritual perspective, a gap reflected in medical textbooks worldwide—nowhere do they explain where the soul goes after leaving the body, as the existence of the spirit remains largely unrecognized in the scientific community. This incomplete understanding of life's truth is akin to an astronomer observing only the daytime sky while ignoring the vastness of the night.

Even though the spiritual world is like the night difficult to perceive with the naked eye, Dharma never encourages blind faith. Instead, it guides followers to analyze, verify, and internalize Dharma teachings through personal understanding and experience. The principle that "human existence does not simply cease with death" is one such example. If you have never encountered this idea before, you should first examine its truth before accepting it.

There are multiple ways to do so. For instance, once you begin reciting the *Great Compassion Mantra*, the *Heart Sutra*, and the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, you may start dreaming of your deceased ancestors or find yourself being chased by one or more individuals (spirits). Why does this happen? Because these are your karmic creditors. Now that you are reciting Buddhist scriptures, you have gained the ability to repay the karmic debts you owe them, so they come to collect just as illustrated in Case 1.

If you have miscarried a baby, you may dream of the baby bidding you farewell, see visions of other pregnant women, or witness a child being taken away by someone after offering Little Houses to help it ascend. In such cases, you usually recognize in the dream that it is your child, even though you do not consciously know them, as they passed away before birth.

After successfully helping the miscarried baby ascend, you will experience noticeable improvements in various aspects of your life—your health may recover, your relationship with your spouse may become more harmonious, your child may stop arguing with you endlessly, and even an autistic child may show signs of recovery.

This is the true Dharma—where theory guides practice, and practice verifies theory. So, what is the difference between Dharma and life sciences? Different people may have different answers. But as both a scientist and a Dharma practitioner, my perspective is this: Dharma reveals the deeper truths of life that science has yet to discover. One of the most fundamental truths is that life consists of both the body and the soul [9,11]. Without this foundational understanding, one cannot truly grasp the essence of Dharma.

This study on CIC once again demonstrates the truth of Dharma's teachings, showing that its wisdom aligns with real-world observations.

From a medical perspective, the mechanism of CIC remains mysterious, and no definitive cure is available. However, from a Dharma perspective, CIC is caused by karma. When karma flares up, spirits occupy the body, leading to illnesses such as CIC.

Since the root cause is clear, the healing method is straightforward: help the spirits ascend and eliminate karma. Once karma is removed and the spirits are liberated, the patient will naturally regain health. Cases 1–7 demonstrate that this entire process from theory to practice is both accurate and effective. Among them, Cases 1, 4, and 5 disclosed the causes of their CIC, while Cases 2, 3, 6, and 7 did not specify their karmic sources.

Case 1: The patient's CIC resulted from abortion and other karmic factors. We have previously discussed how abortion can lead to incurable illnesses, such as lung cancer, lumbar disc herniation, insomnia, Meniere's disease, systemic lupus erythematosus [9], severe depression [23], multiple metastatic cancers, pancreatic cancer [24], asthma [25], facial myasthenia gravis [26], glutaric aciduria type I (GA1) [27], oppositional defiant disorder [20], and parapsychoarchia (schizophrenia) [11]. This study adds CIC to the list of diseases caused by abortion, further illustrating its karmic consequences.

Case 4: The direct karmic cause of her CIC was killing small insects. The *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* is highly effective and convenient for helping small spirits such as insects, fish, and shrimp ascend, producing immediate effects.

Case 5: Her CIC was directly caused by killing and consuming large quantities of live fish, shrimp, chickens, and ducks, leading to severe karmic consequences.

Both Case 4 and Case 5 CIC are caused by killing karma. In the Dharma Decline Age [9], killing karma is a major issue as discussed previously, and many incurable diseases originate from it [9,28].

For cases 2, 3, 6, and 7, where the specific karmic sources remain undisclosed, the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door has nonetheless proven effective in healing them.

When we leave this world, we take nothing with us but our karma (万般带不走, 唯有业随身). If karmic debts are not repaid in this life, they will carry over to the next. We have previously reported several cases of children experiencing retribution for their past-life karma. For example, patient Y52, who engaged in the killing business in a past life, suffered from severe eczema just a few days after birth for over 40 years. Only after encountering Buddhism and resolving her karmic debts did she recover [29]. Another patient, N44, killed two large animals in his past life, resulting in the genetic disorder Glutaric Aciduria Type I [27].

In this study, a one-year-old infant diagnosed with CIC serves as another example (Case 2). At such a young age, she could not have accumulated significant negative karma in this life, indicating that her

suffering stemmed from past-life karma. When her parents helped her eliminate her karmic obstacles, she naturally recovered.

Why have scientists studied CIC for so many years yet failed to develop a definitive theory or cure? This is simply beyond their capability. How could a scientist possibly perceive numerous fish head spirits crowded in a gut (Q&A 2)? No such instruments exist. How could scientists ever link killing karma to CIC? This possibility is not even within their realm of consideration. Human wisdom is limited and can never compare to the boundless wisdom of the Bodhisattva. Therefore, scientific inquiry should be guided by Dharma.

Master Lu emphasizes that Dharma must be applied in daily life, integrating its principles into everyday activities to make life truly filled with Dharma. These cases serve as vivid examples of its practical effectiveness.

Notably, when faced with intractable diseases, even highly knowledgeable medical doctors with access to advanced resources often find themselves powerless.

For example:

Doctor M4 suffered from vertigo for 40 years, which she could not cure despite her medical expertise. However, through Dharma practice, she fully recovered [9].

Doctor X10 was unable to cure her own leukemia, yet she was healed through Buddhism [9].

Doctor G23's mother suffered from Alzheimer's disease, and despite the doctor's efforts, G23 could do little to help. Ultimately, it was Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door that restored her mental clarity [10].

Medical professional N33 struggled with severe asthma for 50 years, which remained untreatable through conventional medicine. Yet, through Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, she was cured in less than two years [25].

In this study (Case 1), the nurse X100 has extensive medical knowledge and access to numerous medical experts in enterology, yet she was unable to cure her own condition. However, through Dharma practice, she ultimately achieved complete recovery from CIC.

These examples illustrate that medical knowledge alone is insufficient to fully explain the true nature of life and illness. Learning from Dharma is essential. Just as observing the sky only during the day provides an incomplete understanding of the universe, relying solely on medical science cannot reveal the full picture of health and healing. Both material and spiritual perspectives must be integrated. When doctors are guided by Dharma, they can encourage patients to practice Dharma to treat incurable diseases, much like how the Buddhist practitioner W89's father's doctor introduced W89 to the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, ultimately leading to her father's recovery from Parkinson's disease [30].

For the treatment CIC, medications can be inconsistent—effective for some individuals while ineffective for others [2]. Similarly, the vibrating capsule has shown efficacy only for a subset of patients [6], and surgery often yields only partial success [7]. The root cause of this variability has long been debated. However, when viewed through the lens of karma and spirit, the underlying mechanism becomes more apparent. If one's karma is heavy, treatments such as purgatives may not work at all or may provide only temporary relief before losing their effectiveness. On the other hand, when karma is light, medical treatments are often significantly more effective.

This phenomenon parallels what is observed in GA1, where individuals with the same genotype can exhibit vastly different phenotypes [27]. When karma is cleared, medications can achieve their full potential. For instance, in cases such as Y97 and A99, the removal of karmic obstacles allowed medical treatments to completely cure their dyshidrosis [28]. Similarly, Buddhist practitioner N43 observed that the same rehabilitation program was effective for her autistic son but not for others whose parents did not. She came to realize that only Buddhism could truly save her son, and that other therapies, at best, serve as supplementary measures. Without the foundation of reciting Buddhist scriptures, other treatments can only provide limited alleviation of symptoms [31].

In managing CIC, we recommend integrating medical treatments with Dharma practices to achieve the best possible outcomes.

Conclusion

This study highlights the limitations of a purely medical approach to CIC and presents an alternative perspective based on Dharma teachings. While modern medicine struggles to provide a definitive cure, the evidence suggests that CIC often stems from karmic obstacles and spiritual interference. The documented cases demonstrate that through Buddhist practices patients have achieved full recovery, even in cases where conventional treatments have failed.

By integrating Dharma practices, individuals suffering from CIC may not only alleviate their physical symptoms but also address the root cause of their condition on a karmic and spiritual level. This study supports the notion that a holistic approach, combining both medical science and Dharma wisdom, offers a more comprehensive path to healing. Therefore, the term "idiopathic" in "chronic idiopathic constipation" should be reinterpreted as a condition influenced by karma and spiritual factors, rather than one with an unknown cause.

These findings encourage further exploration into the intersection of spirituality and health, emphasizing that true healing extends beyond the physical body to encompass the mind and soul.

Acknowledgment

Dharma practitioners Rachel, Shangen, and Purple assisted in the manuscript preparation process. Their work is greatly appreciated.

Conflict of Interest

No.

Financial Support

None.

Ethical Statement

The author did not involve any part of the experimental design, experimental treatments and result analysis of the patients. All the experimental procedures and practices by the presenter were done by themselves independently.

Statement by Translator and Writer

The cases, questions and answers in the text were translated from Chinese to English based on its intended meaning rather than a word-for-word approach. The remaining portions of the paper were written based on my limited understanding of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. If there are any inaccuracies or deviations from the true meaning of the Chinese version, or if the content does not accurately reflect Master Lu's teachings, I sincerely seek forgiveness from the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, all Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, Dharma Protectors, and Master Jun Hong Lu.

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References

1. Zhang W, Zhang L, Meng D, Zhang K, Zhang Z, et al. (2025) F. Novel gut-restricted bivalent agonists targeting mucosal 5-HT4R: Design, synthesis, and biological evaluation. *Eur J Med Chem* 289: 117425.
2. Bassotti G, Usai Satta P, Bellini M (2021) Chronic idiopathic constipation in adults: A review on current guidelines and emerging treatment options. *Clin Exp Gastroenterol* 14: 413-428.
3. Sayuk GS, Waldman SA, Brenner DM (2022) Mechanisms of action of current pharmacologic options for the treatment of chronic idiopathic constipation and irritable bowel syndrome with constipation. *Am J Gastroenterol* 117(4S): S6-S13.

4. Tang J, Li H, Tang W (2021) Efficacy of non-pharmacologic auxiliary treatments in improving defecation function in children with chronic idiopathic constipation: A systematic review and network meta-analysis. *Front Pediatr* 9: 667225.
5. Garzon Mora N, Jaramillo AP (2024) Effectiveness of probiotics in patients with constipation: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Cureus* 16(1): e52013.
6. Curtin BF, Quigley EMM, Chey WD, Lembo AJ, Brenner DM, et al. (2025) The vibrating capsule: Safety and tolerability in patients with chronic idiopathic constipation. *Neurogastroenterol Motil*, pp. e15004.
7. Swanson KA, Phelps HM, Chapman WC Jr, Glasgow SC, Smith RK, et al. (2024) Surgery for chronic idiopathic constipation: Pediatric and adult patients - A systematic review. *J Gastrointest Surg* 28(2): 170-178.
8. Bassotti G, Villanacci V, Corsetti M (2023) Exploring pharmacological treatments for chronic idiopathic constipation in adults: A look back to the future. *J Clin Med* 12(4): 1702.
9. Yang X (2024) Treating rare and intractable diseases via Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. *Health Sci J* 18(5): 1137.
10. Yang X (2024) Alzheimer's diseases are reversible from a Dharma perspective. *Health Sci J*. 2024;18(6):1145.
11. Yang X (2025) Schizophrenia: Etiology, recovery, and prevention. *J Neurol Neurosurg* 1(1): 1-22.
12. Vilanova Sanchez A, Levitt MA (2020) Surgical interventions for functional constipation: An update. *Eur J Pediatr Surg* 30(5): 413-419.
13. Kamiński M, Skonieczna Żydecka K, Łoniewski I, Koulaouzidis A, Marlicz W, et al. (2020) Are probiotics useful in the treatment of chronic idiopathic constipation in adults? A review of existing systematic reviews, meta-analyses, and recommendations. *Prz Gastroenterol* 15(2):103-118.
14. Bharucha AE, Lacy BE (2020) Mechanisms, evaluation, and management of chronic constipation. *Gastroenterology* 158(5): 1232-1249.
15. Lu JH (2012) Master Lu's teachings: Answers to letters of inquiry (47): 10-10.
16. Lu JH (2010) Jun Hong Lu's blog: Explanation of spiritual cases 2(4): 12-29.
17. Lu JH (2020) How to address chronic idiopathic constipation from long-term meat consumption? 13: 17.
18. Lu JH (2012) How to recite scriptures for a child born with chronic idiopathic constipation? *Shuohua* 01: 20.
19. Lu JH (2019) How to relieve chronic idiopathic constipation in the elderly? 03A: 28:28.
20. Yang X (2019) Oppositional defiant disorder: Underlying mechanism and solutions. *WebLog J Fam Med wjfm*. a1502.
21. Yang X (2025) chronic kidney disease: Etiology, recovery, and prevention. *WebLog J Nephrol wjnp*. a0301.
22. Ohrnberger J, Fichera E, Sutton M (2017) The relationship between physical and mental health: A mediation analysis. *Soc Sci Med* 195: 42-49.
23. Yang X (2024) Severe depression: Etiology, recovery, and prevention. *Haya Saudi J Life Sci* 9(11): 427-446.
24. Yang X (2024) Surviving late-stage cancers by practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. *Health Sci J* 18(7): 1155.
25. Yang X (2024) Asthma is curable via Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. *Health Sci J* 18(8): 1165.
26. Yang X (2024) Myasthenia gravis is curable via Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. *Health Sci J* 18(9): 1175.
27. Yang X (2024) Etiology and treatment of glutaric aciduria type I. *J Clin Med Img* 8(3): 1-13.
28. Yang X (2025) Efficiently curing dyshidrosis. *WebLog J Dermatol wjd*. c1901.
29. Yang X (2024) Eczema: Etiology, recovery, and prevention. *WJDC* 1(3): 1-16.
30. Yang X (2025) Parkinson's disease: Etiology, recovery, and prevention. *WebLog J Alzheimers Parkinsons Dis wjapd*. b2501.
31. Yang X (2024) Autism spectrum disorder: Etiology, Recovery, and Prevention. *J Medical and Clinical Case Reports* 1(13).

ISSN: 2574-1241

DOI: 10.26717/BJSTR.2025.61.009571

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